

Effects of Brand Attributes on Word of Mouth: Mediating Role of Brand Trust and Brand Love

Jamshed Ali¹, Rab Nawaz Lodhi², Muhammad Irfan³, Muhammad Shahid Tufail⁴

Abstract

These days, firms are facing intense competition and rising customer expectations in dynamic market conditions. This needs to develop bonding relationships with consumers to get good word of mouth in the market. Despite of literature, there is still gap to underline the empirical relationships of relationship quality, brand trust, brand love and word of mouth in a developing country perspective. Therefore, current study is aimed to empirically analyze the relationship of brand attributes (i.e. brand quality, price perception and brand prestige), and word of mouth while investigating the mediating effect of brand trust, brand love and moderating role of country of origin and switching cost. Non probability sampling technique was followed to collect data from 380 respondents in Pakistan. Structure equation modeling (SEM) was applied using Smart PLS version 3.0 to test proposed hypotheses. Our results revealed that branding attributes have vital role to get word of mouth with double mediation of brand trust and brand love. However, the paths from brand quality, price perception, and brand prestige to word of mouth were not moderated significantly by country of origin and switching cost. The study has implications for policy makers and practitioners to pay more attention on brand quality, price perception, brand prestige, brand trust and brand love rather than on country of origin and switching cost to generate word of mouth in the market.

Keywords: Brand Trust, Brand Love, Switching Costs, Brand attributes, PLS-SEM

1. Introduction

Despite the recession in the global economy, the global home appliance industry is expected to register continuous growth and is forecasted to generate nearly 600 billion U.S. dollars in revenues by 2020. In this respect, large appliances, the first category for domestic use include refrigerators, freezers, air conditioners, and washing machines and accounted for a lion's share of USD 179.5 billion in annual sales in year 2018 in the global market. Overall, the global home appliances market, which was valued at USD 175 billion in 2017 and nearly USD 180 billion in 2018, is projected to reach 203.37 billion US dollar by the end of 2023, registering an annual growth rate of 2.6% p.a. over the forecast period 2018-2023. The small domestic appliances, the second category in juxtaposition, include food processors, toasters, coffee makers, microwave ovens, and water dispensers to name a few. However, the home appliances industry is slowly but steadily changing with the introduction of a new third category comprising of smart connected appliances utilizing the potential of the internet or Internet of Things (IOT). In the coming decades, this third category will have the most potential for growth, particularly among the tech-savvy urban population. Smart washing machines, refrigerators, room air-conditioners and LED TV's, connected to users' mobile phones and capable of talking to each other (inter-connected) are projected for steady growth in the global appliances market.

Some attempts had been made to distinguish between various customer relationship management (CRM) strategies and how important consumers rank them. Marketers implement different methods or approaches of the positive word of mouth using the integrated or network communication sources to create the positive sense or buzz in the minds of the target audiences (Chiu & Chen 2018). WOM refers to sharing an experience gained by using a product or a service from single buyer to alternative, and then the consumer influences another consumer to use that product and gets them in the target audience. This is done by providing authentic communications that are known to transform actions and manners, in workplaces, households, colleges, on websites and long-range interpersonal communication locales (SNSs), anyplace having a casual consumer conversation (Mihic, Radjenovic, & Supic, 2013).

There is holistic or interconnected relationship between the marketing and different marketing practices of the suppliers and finally the catalyst effect is the word of mouth (Crowley, Burton, & Zolkiewski, 2018; Farhan et al, 2020). In the modern marketing environment, the customer and brands in the industry are trying to rely on the new tools of marketing, which include media advertising as well as personal selling. These are very effective and reliable tools. However, the emphasis on word of mouth accompanied by ethics marketing allows the brand not only boost the sales but act as requirements collection for the manufacturers on the global and multicultural basis (Oumlil & Balloun, 2017). It has been found that very fewer studies are conducted having focus on word of mouth with double mediation of Brand Trust and Brand Love with moderation of Country of Origin and Switching Cost while considering White Goods Industry. Research by Heesup Han and Kisang Ryu proposed moderating impact of Switching Cost on some paths (Han & Ryu, 2012). So, the purpose of this study is to fill this gap by analyzing the moderating effect of switching cost and country of origin on word of mouth.

Contextual gap found was to be filled in both contexts Industry and Country. Restaurants, electronic gadgets and devices are studied widely across the globe and different studies have been done in recent years on online word

¹IB&M University of Engineering & Technology, Lahore, Pakistan

²Halley College of Commerce, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan

³Corresponding Author, Division of Management & Administrative Sciences, University of Education, Lower Mall Campus, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴Division of Management & Administrative Sciences, University of Education, Lower Mall Campus, Lahore, Pakistan

of mouth (Baber et al., 2016). Research by Mohammad Reza Jalilvand and Salimpour reveals that some other factors may be added in the model with moderation to understand the behavior of consumers through word of mouth in some other industry (Mohammad Reza Jalilvand, Salimpour, Elyasi, & Mohammadi, 2017; Sajid & Ali, 2018). Word of mouth is considered as the elementary factor in the marketing (Chiu & Chen 2018). Aligning with these studies, objective of study is to interrogate and identify the marketing tactics that create word of mouth, along with brand trust and brand love of customers in white goods industry.

The remainder of paper is structured as follows. Section 1 gives the introduction, while Section 2 throws light on review of literature and hypotheses development. Section 3 elucidates research method used and Section 4 gives demonstration of results of data analysis followed by discussion on findings in Section 5. Section 6 gives implications of the study followed by limitations, future research directions and conclusion in Section 7 and 8 respectively.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

When literature talks about Brand, it means “a specific name, symbol, sign design, or term” which is supportive in recognition of goods or services and helps the consumer to differentiate the product from competitor (Kladou, Kavartzis, Rigopoulou, & Salonika, 2017). According to scholars “Brands act as comfort anchors in the sea of confusion, fear and doubt”. Literature regarding consumer evaluation of wine quality concluded that price and country of origin are most significant contributors related to the perception of wine quality than taste. According to studies, almost 25% of consumers make purchase decisions based on country of origin as cited by Kim & Park, further research shows that a product’s country of origin acts as a signal of product quality, impacts consumer’s perceptions of risk, value and directly affects the possibility of purchase (Park, 2017). Most of the consumers prefer products from developed and industrialized countries because they think these countries have long history of manufacturing and are more competent and are continuously improving their products (Yim Wong, Polonsky, & Garma, 2008).

2.1. Influence of Brand Quality on Brand Trust, WOM and Brand Love

Brand quality refers to judgment of buyer’s expectations about performance (Armstrong, Adam, Denize, & Kotler, 2014). The literature gives conceptual and empirical evidence regarding positive correlation between product or service quality and brand obedience. Pirzad & Karmi, (2015) found a positive relationship between product quality and brand loyalty. When the client receives a decent quality product, trust of the client begins to grow on the manufacturer, and customer believes that the other products or services offered by the company will also be of a good quality. This loyal relationship of the customer and the company can sustain over a long span of time.

As companies try to stress their unique product or service orientation so it could build effective linkage with their clients, this study postulates a strong linkage between the constructs of product quality on brand’s loyalty in the white goods industry. (Pirzad & Karmi, 2015) found a positive relationship between product quality and trust. Literature also supports that BQ has impact on WOM. There is a profound positive relationship between brand quality and word of mouth. Therefore, following hypotheses are proposed:

H₁: Brand quality is positively related to brand trust.

H₂: Brand quality is positively related to WOM.

H₃: Brand quality is positively related to brand love.

2.2. Influence of Price Perception on Brand Trust, WOM and Brand Love

It is evident that cost is the financial expense utilized for a consumer to buy goods or services. It is a fundamental factor that affects consumers buying preference. Consumers more frequently choose the products and services carefully on the viewed price. As discussed by TC Cheng, Lai, & Yeung, (2008) price can be measured through two methods: a sensible price, which tells how this price is perceived by consumers and how this price differentiate the product with its rivals. Furthermore, it also depicts how the customer looks for value of money while purchasing a particular good or service. To conclude the role of price perception is very influencing in consumer behavior to the white goods industry to build Brand trust and Brand love for positive word of mouth. Literature found a significant positive linkage between changes in price acceptance and brand trust. Studies also argue that customer which has higher frequency of purchasing has narrow price acceptance than others, further it shows that high level of trust switches customer focus from price to other aspects (M. R. Jalilvand & Samiei, 2012). In effect, brand quality has an encompassing effect on consumer’s decision-making process and price is a critical factor to determine consumer perception about quality of brand. The study indicate that brand quality and Price perception are key antecedents of brand love (Ng, Butt, Khong, & Ong, 2014). As per discussions above, we suggest the below mentioned hypotheses:

H₄: Price perception is positively related to brand trust.

H₅: Price perception is positively related to WOM.

H₆: Price perception is positively related to brand love.

2.3. Influence of Brand Prestige on Brand Trust, WOM and Brand Love

Brand prestige is a vital element of the luxurious markets (Baek, Kim, & Yu, 2010; Hwang & Han, 2015). In addition, prestigious brand users are treated differently due to their compensation expenses for purchasing of the expensive products (Hwang & Han, 2015). In diverse businesses lot of scholars concentrated on the effect of brand

prestige on decision-making variables, analysis of such studies show that brand prestige has a strong positive effect on brand trust and brand love. Hwang & Hyun, (2012) conducted a study to understand the role of brand prestige in hotel industry and the results clearly showed that brand prestige is a key factor of brand trust and brand love which returns a positive word of mouth by restaurant consumers.

Hwang & Han, (2014) analyzed the effects of prestige brands in cruise industry and revealed that brand prestige is main factor affected on brand trust and brand love which thus make positive word of mouth. Literature found significant positive linkage between brand prestige and brand trust, study shows that brand prestige has a strong positive effect on Brand trust and brand love. (Hwang & Hyun, 2012) Results clearly show that brand prestige is a key factor in brand trust and brand love which in return delivers positive word of mouth by consumers. Scholars while analyzing various business studies concentrated on the effect of brand prestige on decision-making variables. As per discussions above, we suggest the below mentioned hypotheses:

H₇: Brand prestige is positively related to brand trust.

H₈: Brand prestige is positively related to WOM.

H₉: Brand prestige is positively related to brand love.

2.4. Influence of Brand Trust on Brand Love and WOM

Trust has been characterized as one individual trusting that the other individual will fulfill his or her needs. Regarding administration, trust is the feeling held by a client that the specialist co-op would give the administration that addresses purchaser issues. This definition can be utilized as a part of various settings, including trades of items and administrations. Clients believe the specialist co-op in light of the fact that amid the strategy of agreeing to accept administrations, client bolster and evolving administrations, it is conceivable that business delegates are extraordinary.

In earlier studies, trust has been hypothesized as the indicator of fulfillment (Palvia, 2009). Trust or uncertainty often occurs when a relationship is created.(Briggs & Grisaffe, 2010; Senturk & Ali, 2021) figured that client loyalty expressively intervenes the correlation between service performance and attitude intentions. Literature found significant linkage between brand trust and brand love. Satisfaction of consumer for long time towards a product in marketing research is considered as a measure of consumer loyalty, purchase intension and for predicting future purchase intension as well. Brand satisfaction indicator is a weak gauge of consumer, even a satisfied consumer can switch among brand. As per discussions above, we suggest the below mentioned hypotheses:

H₁₀: There is association among brand trust and brand love.

H₁₁: There is association among brand trust and WOM.

H₁₂: There is a mediating role of Brand love between the association of Brand Trust and WOM.

2.5. Influence of Brand Love on WOM

This is a fresh development that brand love is use to examining expansion of consumer brand connections, with a wide decent variety to dynamic sentiments and viewpoints in regards to the brand (Batra, Ahuvia, & Bagozzi, 2012). Scholars classify the features of product affection by planning dissimilar series of components, reliant on their individual meaning of the theory. The common practice is to communicate brand love to social love and struggle to perform positions and senses of the final brand attachment as an effect of the basic comparisons among those theories (Langner, Bruns, Fischer, & Rossiter, 2016).In a couple, the personal and the brand love basis, affiliations stay established by spell, and fondness is the inevitable result of a system, not a prompt outcome (Albert & Merunka, 2013)&(Huber, Meyer, & Schmid, 2015) and (Langner et al., 2016). The outcomes of brand love are loyalty, positive word of mouth, consumer engagement, resistance to negative word of mouth and willingness to pay price premium (Albert, Merunka, & Valette-Florence, 2008; Batra et al., 2012; Carroll & Ahuvia, 2006). Literature also supports that BL has Impact on WOM, earlier studies have shown ideological and empirical evidence to provide a positive correlation between brand love and word of mouth.Literature found significant linkage between brand love and word of mouth. Loyalty with brand and word of mouth are also influenced by Brand Love. It also impacts on customer's repurchase intention or his ability to recognize and desire for continuously buying same brand over the time (Albert & Merunka, 2013). As per discussions above, we suggest the below mentioned hypothesis:

H₁₃: There is association among brand love and WOM.

2.6. Moderating role of Country of Origin

Country of origin of a brand affects the consumer buying decisions. Firms moreover unnoticeably encourage country of origin relationship through their photo names, store format, and styling of things (Shukla, 2011). Be that as it may, new country of origin additionally demonstrates that various purchasers as regularly as conceivable trait the products they buying and use in the wrong republic (Magnusson, Westjohn, & Zdravkovic, 2011).Most of the consumers prefer products from developed and industrialized countries because they think these countries have long history of manufacturing and are more competent and are continuously improving their products (Yim Wong et al., 2008; Ali, 2022).In any case, in the present time of information, finding the correct country of origin is definitely not hard using techniques like verbal questioning , internet organizing, advertisements, headways, and diverse other information sources.

H_{14a}: The impact of brand quality on WOM will be high for those consumers who think country of origin effect on brand quality.

H_{14b}: The impact of price perception on WOM will be high for those consumers who think country of origin effect on price perception.

H_{14c}: The impact of brand prestige on WOM will be high for those consumers who think country of origin effect on brand prestige.

2.7. Moderating role of Switching Cost

Switching costs relate to the costs that a consumer experiences when one changes already in use service or product with a new one. Switching costs cover various financial expenditures including subscription charges, penalties as well as non-financial costs like time and mental stress. In spite of the fact that client’s belief level is short, clients who see high exchanging expenses still frame good social aims for a firm, and in this manner the connection from hope to aims end up noticeably weaker. Not only this, another experimental study in context of china was conducted and it revealed in first experiment that participants from china basically know the characteristics of switching cost impact on their behavior meanwhile the responses of non-Chinese customers are different they tend to show no impact.(Li, Li, Liu, Lages, & Stoet, 2019). Recently a study by Parry &Sarma was conducted by testing the model with iPad customers. They collected data form more than five hundred iPad owners. The core purpose of study was to test the proposed model containing post purchase monetary cost and switching cost study and also to measure the reaction of switchers. Results revealed a significant bidirectional relationship between switching cost and post purchase monetary cost (Parry & Sarma, 2019). As per discussions above, we suggest the below mentioned hypothesis:

H₁₅: The impact of price perception on WOM will be high for those consumers who think switching cost effect on price perception.

2.8. Double Mediation

Dual of double mediation concept lay in the situation where two or more than two mediators are in one indirect relationship, this concept is also known as Multiple Mediators shown in below equation(T. VanderWeele & Vansteelandt, 2014; T. J. VanderWeele & Vansteelandt, 2010). While taking in account the concept that brand image impacts customer satisfaction directly and indirectly through combined impact of Quality and perception. Study by Rauschnabel & Ahuvia revealed that brand quality has a positive impact on brand love while associated with “anthropomorphism” considered as the symbolic quality (Rauschnabel & Ahuvia, 2014). Literature also argued that quality has a positive and strong bounding with uniqueness and prestige. Further study also shows that brand quality has a strong antecedent for satisfaction and loyalty with brand. Recent literature contended that brand quality strengthen the impact of functional concepts with brand love (Bairrada, Coelho, & Coelho, 2018). In a study(Hwang & Han, 2014) analyzed the effects of prestige brands in cruise industry, they revealed that brand prestige is main factor affected on brand trust and brand love which thus makes positive word of mouth . Literature also support that BP has Impact on WOM with double mediation of BT and BL, previous studies have shown ideological and empirical evidence to provide a positive correlation between brand prestige and word of mouth with collective mediation of brand trust and brand love. So, present study also use double mediator concept and develop following relationships.

H₁₆:There is a collective mediation of Brand Trust and Brand love between the associations of Brand Quality and WOM.

H₁₇:There is a collective mediation of Brand Trust and Brand love between the associations of Price Perception and WOM.

H₁₈:There is a collective mediation of Brand Trust and Brand love between the associations of Brand Prestige and WOM.

Fig 1 Research Model

Framework shows the relationship between exogenous and endogenous latent variables consists on a Path Model in three portions. Firstly, measure the influence of three variables respectively, Brand Quality, Price Perception and Brand Prestige on Brand Trust, Brand Love and word of mouth. Secondly, Brand Trust and Brand Love collectively mediate between Brand Quality, Price Perception and Brand Prestige on word of mouth. Lastly measures the moderating effect of Country of Origin between Brand Quality, Price Perception and Brand Prestige on word of mouth, also measure the moderating effect of Switching Costs between Price Perception and word of mouth.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Case selection and Sampling

Focus of the research is white goods industry. The research is considered from consumer's side; the people were likely to involve who are using the consumer electronics. Sample size of questionnaire is 380; data was collected through self-administrated questionnaire from users of white goods industry. Study contacts different segments like professionals, students, and parents, for receiving authentic information. It is impossible to collect the data from a too large population, that's why convenience sampling for the defined population was used.

The purpose of the study is to check the designed hypotheses; a quantitative technique is selected in this study. The research question has a clear connection to the selected research methodology, for testing of our hypotheses data was collected by asking consumers to fill the questionnaire which takes ten minutes maximum. Respondents were selected on the basis of convenience sampling technique; convenience sampling is a type of non-probability sampling technique and it is a technique that is based on the judgment of the researcher. For the easiest access to consumers study use convenience sampling technique.

3.2. Measurement Tools

5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree) was being used to rate the responses. The items were obtained and modified based on the prior research studies Brand Quality (Xie, Batra, & Peng, 2015), Price Perception (TCE Cheng, Lai, & Yeung, 2010), Brand Prestige (Xie et al., 2015) Country of Origin (Kabadayi & Lerman, 2011)&(Lee & Lee, 2011), Brand Trust (Xie et al., 2015), Brand Love and word of mouth. Questionnaire adopted by (Dinh & Mai, 2016), Switching Cost (Buil, De Chernatony, & Martínez, 2013) questionnaires were administrated face to face for removing several ambiguities in the statements of questionnaire and SmartPLS3 was used for analysis of hypotheses through PLS-SEM (Partial Least Square-Structure Equation Modeling) technique.

3.3. Response Rate

Completion or return rate is also known as response rate. This basically indicates percentage of respondents providing response from total sample to the research instrument. (Nulty, 2008) conducted a study to conclude some previous studies for response rate. It shows that majority of previous studies proved that response rate for printed questionnaire is more than online responses. Studies from 1999 till 2006 show that printed response rate is between 55-75%, while a study by Watt et al. in 2002 also show that 32.6% response rate is also good enough for printed questionnaires.

4. Analysis and results

4.1. Demographic Analysis

Demographic analysis discusses stats related to respondent's personal information. In this study demographic part consists of seven questions. Data collected regarding the usage of White Good Products was categorized on Gender, Age, Marital Status, Income, Qualification, Name of Brand and Country of Origin. Table 1 shows the response of first five questions regarding demographic questions, remaining two questions regarding brands and country of origin are shown in Appendix 2.

4.2. Measurement Model Analysis-

4.2.1. Reliability Analysis

Very first test of any analysis is to measure the reliability of data and for this purpose, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite reliability statistics were used. For finding internal consistency, Cronbach's Alpha is a traditional criteria. Cronbach's basically measures the internal consistency of variables that how closely related a set of measurement elements are as a group. Composite reliability is considered a suitable calculator of reliability. The value for Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha should be greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2014).

Table 2 shows reliability statistics of model here Cronbach's as well as composite reliability statistics to support reliability or internal consistency of data. Rule of thumb is that its value should be greater 0.7. As shown in above table value of both reliability statistics Cronbach's Alpha and Composite reliability met the acceptance criteria of all variables in conceptual model. For instance, studies also recommend that in between Cronbach and Composite best criteria is Composite reliability.

4.2.2. Validity Analysis

Validity of instrument and data measures through two tests Convergent and Discriminant validity. Convergent validity determines all those confluences of pointers that show that how a construct compares the items evaluating the other constructs Convergent Validity can be defined as a degree to which all the compound items of the model are being used to evaluate and assess at the very same concept (Suriyenti, Ramayah, Lo, & Tarmizi, 2014; Arshad

et al.,2020). Convergent Validity is measured by using Average Variance Extracted and the Factor Loading values of items. Simply it is the concept that variables and items are theoretically correlated and having the same concept. Discriminant validity assessment use to ensure that a reflective construct has the strongest relationships with its own indicators or items, that's why here comparison done with other constructs (J. F. Hair Jr, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2017). Discriminant validity shows different concepts of items and their constructs, it is basically the square root of Average Variance Extracted (Surienty et al., 2014). This is measured by two tests, Fornell-Larcker criterion and Cross-loadings of items.

Table 1: Demographic Profile

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	237	62.4	62.4	62.4
	Female	143	37.6	37.6	100
	Total	380	100	100	
Age	Below 18	3	0.8	0.8	0.8
	18-25	117	30.8	30.8	31.6
	25-35	189	49.7	49.7	81.3
	35-45	52	13.7	13.7	95
	45-55	16	4.2	4.2	99.2
	55+	3	0.8	0.8	100
	Total	380	100	100	
Marital Status	Single	192	50.5	50.5	50.5
	Married	188	49.5	49.5	100
	Total	380	100	100	
Income	Less than 50,000	159	41.8	41.8	41.8
	50,000-80,000	111	29.2	29.2	71.1
	80,000-110,000	40	10.5	10.5	81.6
	110,000-140,000	18	4.7	4.7	86.3
	140,000+	52	13.7	13.7	100
	Total	380	100	100	
Education	Senior School	23	6.1	6.1	6.1
	Bachelors	145	38.2	38.2	44.2
	Masters	193	50.8	50.8	95
	Doctorate	9	2.4	2.4	97.4
	Others	10	2.6	2.6	100
	Total	380	100	100	

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
BL	0.932	0.944
BP	0.821	0.893
BQ	0.816	0.891
BT	0.876	0.924
COO	0.878	0.911
COO mod BP > WOM	1.000	1.000
COO mod BQ > WOM	1.000	1.000
COO mod PP > WOM	1.000	1.000
PP	0.840	0.893
SC	0.920	0.937
SC mod PP > WOM	1.000	1.000
WOM	0.915	0.940

Note: BQ (Brand Quality), BT (Brand Trust), BL (Brand Love), WOM (Word of Mouth), BP (Brand Power), COO (Country of Origin), PP (Price Perception).

4.2.3. Factor Analysis

Henseler et al debated that minimum 50 per cent of indicator variance of measure must be explained by the latent variable (Jorg Henseler, Ringle, & Sinkovics, 2009). Factor loading value of each item should be greater than 0.7, which shows that the question is actually a good measure for the construct. Study by Hair et al., recommended by that 0.6 factor loading is also acceptable but when it's not disturbing the reliability of data. Average Variance

Extracted defined as “the degree which shows support the convergent validity or shows the certainty of model” (Joseph F Hair Jr, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2016). This measures amount of variance that is captured by construct in relation to amount of Variance due to measurement error. Hair, et al., recommended that value for each construct should be greater than 0.5 showing goodness of AVE. Variance inflation factor measures the extent to which the variance of the estimated regression coefficients is enhanced as comparatively to the situation when the predictor variables are not being linearly related. Book of Hair et al., 2016 revealed that VIF estimated that “how much the variance of the estimated regression coefficients is magnified as compared to when the predictor variables are not linearly related”. In short this demonstrates that how much the variance is exaggerated or overestimated. Basically, this is a degree of Multi collinearity in facts & figures. The value for VIF should be less than 5, for both inner and outer model.

Table 3: Factor Loading and AVE

Items	Factor Loading	VIF	Average Variance Extract	Items	Factor Loading	VIF	Average Variance Extracted
BL1	0.822	2.667	0.677	BT1	0.914	2.764	0.801
BL2	0.832	3.076		BT2	0.895	2.528	
BL3	0.841	3.320		BT3	0.876	2.094	
BL5	0.852	3.362		COO1	0.751	1.588	0.674
BL6	0.855	3.329		COO2	0.832	2.297	
BL8	0.806	2.433		COO3	0.864	2.617	
BL9	0.781	3.005		COO4	0.801	2.183	
BL10	0.789	2.934		COO5	0.85	2.601	
BP2	0.844	1.787		SC1	0.86	3.173	
BP3	0.876	1.995	SC2	0.846	3.024		
BP4	0.853	1.778	SC3	0.833	2.431		
BQ1	0.849	1.823	SC4	0.875	4.854		
BQ2	0.846	1.763	SC5	0.848	4.699		
BQ3	0.870	1.841	SC6	0.799	2.831	0.798	
PP1	0.811	1.720	WO	0.871	2.520		
PP2	0.849	2.235	M1	0.902	3.187		
PP3	0.845	2.213	WO	0.924	3.831		
PP4	0.781	1.611	M3	0.874	2.638		
			M4				

Table 3 representing the results of factor loadings after deleting the unreliable questions on the bases of their outer loading values and AVE, here all the questions are reliable enough by showing the value more than 0.7. So, on the whole these question’s data will be used for further model testing. Further Table also shows the results of AVE of variables present in measurement model. Table shows that each construct met the criteria to support convergent validity. According to AVE results, value for each construct is good enough which shows the goodness of convergent validity and the values are in the rage of 0.674 as minimum value and 0.801 as maximum value for brand trust showing that all the variables are having value more than 0.5. Table also shows the VIF values for outer model or items used as instrument. As explained that value should be less than 5, in present study values for outer model, minimum value is 1.588 of the first question of country of origin and maximum value is 4.854 for

the fourth question of switching cost. All remaining values are in range and accept the criteria to being less than 5.

4.2.4. Discriminant Validity

Very first criterion for checking discriminant validity is Fornell-Larcker criterion. This concept has a requirement that variable should have a maximum correlation with itself and lower with other constructs. This value is basically the square root of Average Variance Extracted value of respective variable. According to criteria of Hair et al., value of each construct should be greater than 0.7, further more upper diagonal values of table should be maximum which shows that variables having different concept then other variables consisting in the measurement model. Second criterion to measure the discriminant validity is through cross loading analysis. This shows the factor loading values of items with their own construct as well as with other constructs. Here concept discusses that each item should have a maximum loading value with its own construct and less with other variables present in the measurement model.

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker criterion

	BL	BP	BQ	BT	COO	PP	SC	WOM
BL	0.823							
BP	0.615	0.858						
BQ	0.642	0.549	0.855					
BT	0.740	0.687	0.691	0.895				
COO	0.614	0.474	0.451	0.503	0.821			
PP	0.530	0.445	0.463	0.516	0.420	0.822		
SC	0.435	0.254	0.209	0.294	0.449	0.503	0.844	
WOM	0.749	0.566	0.565	0.618	0.564	0.439	0.374	0.893

Note: BQ (Brand Quality), BT (Brand Trust), BL(Brand Love), WOM (Word of Mouth), BP(Brand Power),COO (Country of Origin), PP (Price Perception)

Table 4 shows the results of Larcker criterion, value of each variable as correlation, only upper diagonal values should be maximum and have consideration and all the values should be greater than 0.7. To support discriminant validity, another criterion is that remaining values of that column should be lower than the top one. In present study upper diagonal values are between the range of 0.821 as minimum and 0.895 as maximum value showing that data support the concept of discrimination.

Table 5 shows the cross-loading values of construct's items with their own constructs as well as compare with other constructs. The maximum value for its own construct shows that question is good and suitable measure for that concept. Here table clearly represented that values of indicators are up to the mark with its own construct and lesser with others which support the analysis.

4.2.5. Structural Model Analysis

Structured equation modeling (SEM) is used to measure the relationships and coefficient among the latent variables(Khan et al.,2020) . The power of path coefficient shows the strength of relationship among Latent Variables and positive and negative value of path coefficient has to be corresponding to the direction of pre-proposed relationship (Joseph F Hair Jr et al., 2016). This study evaluated Inner and outer model in this step, outer model reveals the factor analysis whereas inner model shows the coefficient and direction & significance of relationships between exogenous and endogenous variables (J. Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Model fit was measured by SRMR which is defined as “the difference amongst the observed correlation and predicted correlation of the variables i.e. constructs” (F. Hair Jr, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & G. Kuppelwieser, 2014). Its value should be less than 0.10 which is being considered to be a good fit value (Hu & Bentler, 1999). Other criteria are use of NFI and Chi-Square as higher value of Chi-Square shows the goodness index. Result shows the values of SRMR and Chi-Square and other goodness index. For structured model value of SRMR is 0.054 and for estimated model is 0.073 both of the values is less than 0.10 which shows fitness of model. Value of Chi-Square is also greater than the criteria which is “value should be greater than 19.58” for both structured and estimated model.

Figure 2 shows the results of algorithm analysis; here only inner model is shown and outer model was to avoid the complexity of model representation. Here two values shown; first one is “Path Coefficient” and second one is “R Square” values of dependent variables. Furthermore, figure just shows path coefficients of direct, path model and moderators so mediation couldn't be explained here. Figure also shows the value of R2 for three variables, which is considered as dependent (Brand Love, Brand Trust and Word of Mouth) but originally only word of mouth is dependent and other two are mediator. Coefficient of determination is used to analyze the structural model which has most predictive accuracy used to calculate by squaring correlation between actual and predicted values of a specific construct. Starting from value of Brand Love is 0.612 which shows that brand love is measured 61.2% due to its independents, and Brand Trust has a value of 0.630 means 63% trust is measured through independent variables. At the end word of mouth have a value 0.603 which shows 60.3% measured through its independent variables. On the whole all the values are good enough to meet the criteria.

Hypotheses are tested through bootstrapping analysis. This concept carries the subsampling concept. Acceptance of hypotheses lay on T statistics and P Value criteria by Hair et al. Table 6 used for hypotheses testing and

acceptance status. On bases of T and P value, those hypotheses which are having T value greater than 1.96 and P value less than 0.05 are being accepted.

Table 5: Cross Loading

	Brand Love	Brand Prestige	Brand Quality	Brand Trust	Country of Origin	Price Perception	Switching Cost	word of mouth
BL1	0.822	0.564	0.591	0.676	0.506	0.490	0.316	0.595
BL2	0.832	0.543	0.582	0.693	0.504	0.446	0.337	0.635
BL3	0.841	0.555	0.557	0.666	0.546	0.439	0.367	0.602
BL5	0.852	0.529	0.553	0.667	0.485	0.467	0.354	0.611
BL6	0.855	0.494	0.546	0.604	0.512	0.411	0.392	0.637
BL8	0.806	0.486	0.508	0.566	0.483	0.446	0.346	0.592
BL9	0.781	0.420	0.438	0.494	0.492	0.405	0.387	0.617
BL10	0.789	0.443	0.431	0.471	0.516	0.375	0.375	0.646
BP2	0.534	0.844	0.452	0.557	0.406	0.379	0.184	0.451
BP3	0.521	0.876	0.488	0.610	0.385	0.395	0.205	0.500
BP4	0.530	0.853	0.473	0.600	0.431	0.372	0.262	0.504
BQ1	0.525	0.426	0.849	0.555	0.332	0.410	0.198	0.454
BQ2	0.518	0.472	0.846	0.588	0.393	0.379	0.126	0.474
BQ3	0.599	0.507	0.870	0.627	0.427	0.400	0.211	0.519
BT1	0.669	0.641	0.648	0.914	0.434	0.449	0.259	0.565
BT2	0.630	0.623	0.618	0.895	0.413	0.402	0.214	0.535
BT3	0.686	0.581	0.591	0.876	0.502	0.532	0.316	0.558
COO1	0.485	0.386	0.387	0.384	0.751	0.335	0.383	0.482
COO2	0.471	0.438	0.394	0.452	0.832	0.314	0.315	0.441
COO3	0.516	0.448	0.425	0.494	0.864	0.401	0.364	0.498
COO4	0.476	0.339	0.294	0.356	0.801	0.308	0.357	0.403
COO5	0.564	0.329	0.337	0.367	0.850	0.354	0.416	0.479
PP1	0.484	0.422	0.417	0.465	0.374	0.811	0.392	0.389
PP2	0.405	0.364	0.376	0.401	0.356	0.849	0.404	0.337
PP3	0.381	0.318	0.358	0.400	0.285	0.845	0.413	0.331
PP4	0.456	0.346	0.363	0.418	0.355	0.781	0.441	0.376
SC1	0.429	0.255	0.214	0.311	0.391	0.525	0.860	0.382
SC2	0.334	0.202	0.122	0.238	0.328	0.438	0.846	0.320
SC3	0.404	0.219	0.177	0.268	0.383	0.484	0.833	0.333
SC4	0.356	0.248	0.200	0.264	0.400	0.397	0.875	0.314
SC5	0.313	0.192	0.174	0.187	0.374	0.328	0.848	0.264
SC6	0.343	0.142	0.163	0.186	0.403	0.312	0.799	0.245
WO M1	0.655	0.536	0.548	0.558	0.524	0.406	0.296	0.871
WO M2	0.658	0.487	0.462	0.558	0.463	0.377	0.344	0.902
WO M3	0.702	0.483	0.506	0.563	0.507	0.397	0.336	0.924
WO M4	0.660	0.516	0.503	0.529	0.521	0.387	0.359	0.874

Note: BQ (Brand Quality), BT (Brand Trust), BL(Brand Love), WOM (Word of Mouth), BP(Brand Power)

4.2.6. Double Mediation Test

Concept of double mediation lays in the situation where two or more than two mediators take place in one indirect relationship, this concept is also known as Multiple Mediators (T. VanderWeele & Vansteelandt, 2014; T. J. VanderWeele & Vansteelandt, 2010). In this study double mediation tested through impact of Brand Quality on Brand Trust and Brand Love then on word of mouth, same double mediation tested through Price Perception on Brand Trust and Brand Love then on word of mouth. Same test followed for the impact of Brand Prestige on Brand Trust and Brand Love on word of mouth.

Figure 1: Results of Structural Model

Table 6: PLS-SEM Path Analysis

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	T Statistics	P Values	Results
BQ -> BT	0.402	0.403	8.466	0.000	Supported
BQ -> WOM	0.100	0.097	2.009	0.045	Supported
BQ -> BL	0.198	0.197	3.798	0.000	Supported
PP -> BT	0.152	0.153	4.026	0.000	Supported
PP -> WOM	-0.010	-0.011	0.217	0.829	Not Supported
PP -> BL	0.155	0.160	3.793	0.000	Supported
BP -> BT	0.399	0.398	7.397	0.000	Supported
BP -> WOM	0.119	0.120	2.356	0.019	Supported
BP -> BL	0.149	0.152	2.807	0.005	Supported
BT -> BL	0.421	0.417	7.344	0.000	Supported
BT -> WOM	0.034	0.030	0.540	0.589	Not Supported
BT -> BL -> WOM	0.207	0.203	5.360	0.000	Supported
BL -> WOM	0.492	0.488	6.918	0.000	Supported
COO mod BQ > WOM	0.015	0.013	0.355	0.723	Not Supported
COO mod PP > WOM	0.021	0.020	0.523	0.601	Not Supported
COO mod BP > WOM	0.002	0.003	0.042	0.967	Not Supported
SC mod PP > WOM	0.030	0.029	0.839	0.402	Not Supported
					Supported

Note: BQ (Brand Quality), BT (Brand Trust), BL (Brand Love), WOM (Word of Mouth), BP (Brand Power)

Double mediation hypotheses were tested through bootstrapping analysis. For significance of relationship each hypothesis uses Hair et al., acceptance criteria that T value should greater than 1.96, results shows that all three mediations are having significant values for acceptance.

Table 7: Double Mediation Test

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Value	Results
BQ -> BT -> BL -> WOM	0.083	0.082	0.020	4.112	0.000	Supported
PP -> BT -> BL -> WOM	0.032	0.031	0.009	3.420	0.001	Supported
BP -> BT -> BL -> WOM	0.083	0.081	0.018	4.577	0.000	Supported

Note: BQ (Brand Quality), BT (Brand Trust), BL(Brand Love), WOM (Word of Mouth), BP(Brand Power)

5. Discussion

Core objective of this research was to check; are marketing tactics (i.e. brand quality, brand prestige and price perception) are remedy to create word of mouth in the presence of brand trust and brand love with moderation of country of origin and switching cost, and to check the mediation of brand trust and brand love on said relationship. In White goods industry word of mouth plays a vital role to take purchase decisions. When customer brings a brand into consideration, he or she considers amount of information or size of word of mouth in context of specific brand. Customers use this to minimize the risk while making a buying decision. Consumers normally get feedback from their circle about product, company and country of origin before taking any decisions. White Good products considered as luxury and tech savvy products all over the world. This industry is a million-dollar industry and this is a big challenge for marketers to create a word of mouth in this competitive market through using different marketing tactics like brand quality, price perceptions and brand prestige.

In this study, it was analyzed that brand quality, price perception and brand prestige show significant effect on word of mouth, while significant mediation of brand trust and brand love on relationship of marketing tactics (i.e. brand quality, price perception, brand prestige) and word of mouth. But moderation of country of origin and switching cost didn't show any significant effect on word of mouth. Customers consider country of origin while buying high involvement products and it becomes less important in evaluation of low involvement products. Country of origin is an extrinsic cue and consumers just consider it while they lack information of intrinsic cues (Zdravkovic, 2013). White goods industry is a tech savvy industry and house hold product consumers show less involvement in product and country of origin become less important while considering the white good products. For Switching cost an experimental study was conducted on china which revealed that switching cost has impact on their behavior. However, foreign customers in China demonstrated had no impact of switching cost (Li et al., 2019). As per study, results suggest marketers need to focus on improving brand quality, price perception and brand prestige rather than focusing on country of origin and switching cost to get word of mouth. Marketers can use these marketing tactics of brand quality, price perception and brand prestige to develop consumer brand trust and brand love which will help to create good word of mouth about brand in the marketplace.

5.1. Implications

This study provides clear understanding to marketers about branding attributes as remedy to create word of mouth in the presence of brand trust and brand love while analyzing moderating role of country of origin and switching cost effect. Competition is becoming aggressive day by day in white goods industry and this is a big challenge for marketers to create positive word of mouth in the marketplace. In white goods industry consumers always discuss with their friends, family members, colleagues and especially with dealers who are dealing with these luxury products on daily basis. So, in this context word of mouth is very important to increase sales volume. Marketers need to work on organic word of mouth in the market for that purpose they need to focus on product quality, competitive price and brand prestige and from that they can generate brand trust and brand love.

Country of origin and switching cost had no significant effect on word of mouth, so marketers need to focus on other areas rather than to invest on image of country of origin and switching costs. So as per theoretical support and real-world practices in the market our study supports the facts. We suggest marketers to work on brand quality improvement, brand competitive price and brand prestige to improve brand trust and brand love in the consumers' minds which create good and positive word of mouth in the market. Also consider the consumer demands regarding product features, colour, and live demos of products and after sales service to increase positive word of mouth in the market.

5.2. Limitations and future research

This study examines that marketing tactics are really a remedy to create word of mouth in the presence of brand trust and brand love, also test the moderation of country of origin and switching cost by the use of the survey research system. Despite the fact that it develops another test model which in light of previous researches and

academic knowledge; this research has a few limitations and future research guidelines as take after: Firstly, many other important variables not considered in this study for example consumer experience, brand commitment, customer satisfaction, loyalty and perceived value, which might impact on word of mouth. In this study these variables are not considered, in this way advance research needs to contain more strategies, keeping in mind the end goal to increase better knowledge for academics as well as for professional marketer. Secondly, this study used convenience-sampling method and sample may be biased with certain type of respondents. Thirdly, the study only focused on white goods industry. Further studies might be conducted on luxury products like automobiles, fashion industry, mobile phone & laptop industry, tourism industry and hotel industry. Research can also be conducted as a comparative study by combining two different industries. Another possible limitation is the reviewed papers and studies might be weak in methodology other than the sample size and measurement error taken into account in this study.

6. Conclusion

This study gives equally theory development to academics and suggestions for professional marketers and brand managers to implement marketing tactics to create word of mouth. Taking into account past theories and studies about with respect to word of mouth and its results, this study indicates clear connections between all variables mentioned in the model. The results of this research also provide essential proof for professionals who take responsibility to generate word of mouth in the industry.

References

- Albert, N., & Merunka, D. (2013). The role of brand love in consumer-brand relationships. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 30(3), 258-266.
- Albert, N., Merunka, D., & Valette-Florence, P. (2008). When Consumers Love Their Brands: Exploring The Concept and its Dimensions. *Journal of Business Research*, 61(10), 1062-1075.
- Ali, A. (2022). Foreign Debt, Financial Stability, Exchange Rate Volatility and Economic Growth in South Asian Countries. *Journal of Business and Economic Options*.
- Armstrong, G., Adam, S., Denize, S., & Kotler, P. (2014). *Principles of marketing*: Pearson Australia.
- Arshad, M. Z., Meirun, T., Ahmad, M. J., Ali, M., Arshad, M. H., & Maneerat, C. (2020). The Importance of Learning Orientation and Entrepreneurial Orientation on SMEs Performance. *International Journal of Disaster Recovery and Business Continuity*, 11(1), 1220-1228.
- Baber, A., Thurasamy, R., Malik, M. I., Sadiq, B., Islam, S., & Sajjad, M. (2016). Online word-of-mouth antecedents, attitude and intention-to-purchase electronic products in Pakistan. *Telematics and Informatics*, 33(2), 388-400.
- Baek, T. H., Kim, J., & Yu, J. H. (2010). The differential roles of brand credibility and brand prestige in consumer brand choice. *Psychology & Marketing*, 27(7), 662-678.
- Bairrada, C. M., Coelho, F., & Coelho, A. (2018). Antecedents and outcomes of Brand Love: Utilitarian and Symbolic Brand Qualities. *European Journal of Marketing*, 52(3/4), 656-682.
- Batra, R., Ahuvia, A., & Bagozzi, R. P. (2012). Brand Love. *Journal of Marketing*, 76(2), 1-16.
- Briggs, E., & Grisaffe, D. (2010). Service performance—loyalty intentions link in a business-to-business context: The role of relational exchange outcomes and customer characteristics. *Journal of Service Research*, 13(1), 37-51.
- Buil, I., De Chernatony, L., & Martínez, E. (2013). Examining the role of advertising and sales promotions in brand equity creation. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(1), 115-122.
- Carroll, B. A., & Ahuvia, A. C. (2006). Some antecedents and outcomes of Brand Love. *Marketing Letters*, 17(2), 79-89.
- Cheng, T., Lai, L., & Yeung, A. (2010). The Driving Forces of Customer Loyalty: A Study of Internet Service Providers in Hong Kong *Transforming E-Business Practices and Applications: Emerging Technologies and Concepts* (pp. 44-61): IGI Global.
- Cheng, T., Lai, L., & Yeung, A. C. (2008). The driving forces of customer loyalty: a study of internet service providers in Hong Kong. *International journal of e-business research*, 4(4), 26-42.
- Chiu, Y.-L., & Chen, L.-J. (2018). Studying the relationship between the perceived value of online group-buying websites and customer loyalty: the moderating role of referral rewards. *Journal Of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 33(5), 665 - 679.
- Crowley, E., Burton, J., & Zolkiewski, J. (2018). Servitization intent as a factor in the servitization process. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 33(8), 1125 - 1140.
- Dinh, T. D., & Mai, K. N. (2016). Guerrilla marketing's effects on Gen Y's word-of-mouth intention—a mediation of credibility. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 28(1), 4-22.
- F. Hair Jr, J., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & G. Kuppelwieser, V. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) An emerging tool in business research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106-121.

- Farhan, M., Hussain, R. I., Khan, S. N., Tahir, M. S., & Bhatti, H (2020). The Relationship Among The Corporate Reputation, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty And Behavioral Intentions. A Study On The Pakistan Textile Industry. *International Journal of Disaster Recovery and Business Continuity*, Vol.11, No. 3, , pp. 01–13
- Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*: Sage publications.
- Hair Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*: Thousand Oakes, CA: Sage.
- Hair, F., J., Hult, M., G., Ringle, M., C., & Sarste. (2014). A PRIMER ON PARTIAL LEAST SQUARES STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING (PLS-SEM). *Thousand Oaks: Sage*.
- Han, H., & Ryu, K. (2012). Key factors driving customers' word-of-mouth intentions in full-service restaurants: The moderating role of switching costs. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 53(2), 96-109.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 115-135.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The Use of Partial Least Squares Path Modeling In International Marketing. *New Challenges to International Marketing advances in international marketing*, 277-319.
- Hu, L. T., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff Criteria for fit indexes in Covariance Structure Analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1-55.
- Huber, F., Meyer, F., & Schmid, D. A. (2015). Brand love in progress—the interdependence of brand love antecedents in consideration of relationship duration. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 24(6), 567-579.
- Hwang, J., & Han, H. (2014). Examining strategies for maximizing and utilizing brand prestige in the luxury cruise industry. *Tourism Management*, 40, 244-259.
- Hwang, J., & Han, H. (2015). Understanding other customer perceptions in the private country club industry. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 20(8), 875-896.
- Hwang, J., & Hyun, S. S. (2012). The antecedents and consequences of brand prestige in luxury restaurants. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 17(6), 656-683.
- Jalilvand, M. R., & Samiei, N. (2012). The impact of Electronic word of mouth on a Tourism Destination choice: Testing the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). *Internet Research: Electronic Networking Applications and Policy*, 22(5), 591-612.
- Jalilvand, M. R., Salimipour, S., Elyasi, M., & Mohammadi, M. (2017). Factors influencing word of mouth behaviour in the restaurant industry. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 35(1), 81-110.
- Kabadayi, S., & Lerman, D. (2011). Made in China but sold at FAO Schwarz: country-of-origin effect and trusting beliefs. *International Marketing Review*, 28(1), 102-126.
- Khan, H., Rehmat, M., Butt, T. H., Farooqi, S., & Asim, J. (2020). Impact of transformational leadership on work performance, burnout and social loafing: a mediation model. *Future Business Journal*, 6(1), 1-13.
- Kladou, S., Kavaratzis, M., Rigopoulou, I., & Salonika, E. (2017). The role of Brand Elements in Destination Branding. *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, 6(4), 426-435.
- Langner, T., Bruns, D., Fischer, A., & Rossiter, J. R. (2016). Falling in love with brands: a dynamic analysis of the trajectories of brand love. *Marketing letters*, 27(1), 15-26.
- Lee, H.-M., & Lee, C.-C. (2011). Country-of-origin and brand redeployment impact after brand acquisition. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 28(6), 412-420.
- Li, X., Li, B., Liu, X., Lages, M., & Stoet, G. (2019). Task-switching costs disappear if non-chinese participants respond to chinese characters. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*.
- Magnusson, P., Westjohn, S. A., & Zdravkovic, S. (2011). “What? I thought Samsung was Japanese”: accurate or not, perceived country of origin matters. *International Marketing Review*, 28(5), 454-472.
- Mihic, S., Radjenovic, D., & Supic, D. (2013). CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR-BUILDING MARKETING STRATEGY. *Metalurgia International*, 18(8), 116.
- Ng, P. F., Butt, M. M., Khong, K. W., & Ong, F. S. (2014). Antecedents of Green Brand Equity: An integrated approach. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 121(2), 203-215.
- Nulty, D. D. (2008). The adequacy of response rates to online and paper surveys: what can be done? *Assessment & evaluation in higher education*, 33(3), 301-314.
- Oumlil, A. B., & Balloun, J. L. (2017). Cultural variations and ethical business decision making: a study of individualistic and collective cultures. *Journal Of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 32(7), 889-900.
- Palvia, P. (2009). The role of trust in e-commerce relational exchange: A unified model. *Information & management*, 46(4), 213-220.
- Park, K. (2017). The impact of country of origin on context effects in choice. *International Marketing Review*.
- Parry, M. E., & Sarma, S. (2019). The impact of pioneer adopter characteristics and perceptions on the perceived costs of switching to a follower product. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 24.

- Pirzad, A., & Karmi, E. (2015). Studying the Relationship between Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty through Perceived Value and Trust. *Journal of Social Issues & Humanities*, 3(3), 275-281.
- Rauschnabel, P. A., & Ahuvia, A. C. (2014). You're so lovable: Anthropomorphism and Brand Love. *Journal of Brand Management*, 21(5), 372-395.
- Sajid, A. & Ali, A. (2018). Inclusive Growth and Macroeconomic Situations in South Asia: An Empirical Analysis. *Bulletin of Business and Economics (BBE)*, 7(3), 97-109.
- Şentürk, İ., & Ali, A. (2021). Socioeconomic Determinants of Gender Specific Life Expectancy in Turkey: A Time Series Analysis. *Sosyoekonomi*, 29(49), 85-111.
- Shukla, P. (2011). Impact of interpersonal influences, brand origin and brand image on luxury purchase intentions: Measuring interfunctional interactions and a cross-national comparison. *Journal of world business*, 46(2), 242-252.
- Suriyanti, L., Ramayah, T., Lo, M. C., & Tarmizi, A. N. (2014). Quality of Work Life and Turnover Intention: A Partial Least Square (PLS) Approach. *Social Indicators Research*, 119(1), 405-420.
- VanderWeele, T. J., & Vansteelandt, S. (2010). Odds Ratios for Mediation Analysis for a Dichotomous Outcome. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 172(12), 1339-1348.
- VanderWeele, T., & Vansteelandt, S. (2014). Mediation Analysis with Multiple Mediators. *Epidemiologic Methods*, 2(1), 95-115.
- Xie, Y., Batra, R., & Peng, S. (2015). An extended model of preference formation between global and local brands: The roles of identity expressiveness, trust, and affect. *Journal of International Marketing*, 23(1), 50-71.
- Yim Wong, C., Polonsky, M. J., & Garma, R. (2008). The impact of consumer ethnocentrism and country of origin sub-components for high involvement products on young Chinese consumers' product assessments. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 20(4), 455-476.
- Zdravkovic, S. (2013). Does country-of-origin matter to Generation Y? *Young Consumers*, 14(1), 89-102.

Appendix 1: Brands & Country of Origin

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Brands	Haier	139	36.6	36.6	36.6
	Gree Electric	29	7.6	7.6	44.2
	ChangHongRuba	7	1.8	1.8	46.1
	Orient	32	8.4	8.4	54.5
	PEL	23	6.1	6.1	60.5
	Dawlance	70	18.4	18.4	78.9
	Samsung	43	11.3	11.3	90.3
	LG	12	3.2	3.2	93.4
	Mitsubishi	6	1.6	1.6	95
	Kenwood	5	1.3	1.3	96.3
	Electrolux	1	0.3	0.3	96.6
	Panasonic	3	0.8	0.8	97.4
	Others	10	2.6	2.6	100
Total	380	100	100		
Country of Origin	Pakistan	263	69.2	69.2	69.2
	China	57	15	15	84.2
	Korea	14	3.7	3.7	87.9
	UK	4	1.1	1.1	88.9
	Japan	25	6.6	6.6	95.5
	Others	17	4.5	4.5	100
	Total	380	100	100	